

Copper(II) Complexes of 3-Aldehydosalicylic Acid and its Schiff Bases

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FOR the past several years we have been studying the metallic complexes of 3-aldehydosalicylic acid (= ASA-H₂) and its Schiff bases with monoamines and diamines¹. This note describes the isolation and characterization of some copper(II) complexes with 3-aldehydosalicylic acid and its Schiff bases with aniline (= ASAA-H₂), methylamine (= ASAMA-H₂), and ethanolamine (= ASAENOL-H₂). All of these complexes except one, are binuclear with subnormal magnetic moments at room temperature. Tanaka *et al.*^{2,3} recently reported the isolation and characterization of some binuclear copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes of ASA-H₂ and its Schiff bases with alkylamines.

Experimental

3-Aldehydosalicylic acid was prepared as described previously¹. Schiff bases were prepared by usual procedures. Magnetic susceptibilities at room temperatures were measured by Gouy balance. Faraday method was used for the measurements of magnetic susceptibilities from liquid nitrogen temperature to room temperature. The Pascal constants⁴ were used for diamagnetic correction. Infrared spectra were measured in KBr phase and nujol mull. Some of the i.r. spectra were measured in hexachlorobutadiene also. Electronic spectra in nujol mull were run in Spectromom spectrophotometer, whereas the solution spectra were run in Beckman Du-2 spectrophotometer.

Preparation of the copper(II) complexes :

$Cu_2Cl_2(ASA)H_2O$, (I) : Copper(II) chloride dihydrate (1.27 g, 0.0075 mole) in 30 ml of absolute alcohol was mixed with ASA-H₂ (1.2 g, 0.0075 mole) in 30 ml of absolute alcohol. The green solution (A), thus obtained, was refluxed (2 hr) on water-bath and then filtered while hot (pH of the solution was ≈ 3). The volume of the filtrate was reduced to half and then treated with anhydrous sodium acetate (0.60 g, 0.0075 mole). It was then heated on water-bath for five minutes while green crystalline compound was separated out, filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuo. Found : C, 25.71; H, 1.48; Cl, 19.08; Cu, 33.59%; μ_{eff} = 0.72 B.M. at 30° (per Cu atom); ν_{max} (nujol mull), 12.2 kK; ν_{max} (in pyridine), 14.5 kK (log ϵ = 2.4); Calc. for (I) C, 25.26; H, 1.57; Cl, 18.68; Cu, 33.42%.

$Cu_2Cl_2(ASA-H)_2H_2O$ (II) : The green solution (A), on slow evaporation, gave this green crystalline complex, washed with dry ethanol and dried in vacuo. Found : C, 35.49; H, 1.98; Cl, 13.22; Cu,

23.75%; μ_{eff} = 0.58 B.M. at 29.8° (per Cu atom); ν_{max} (Nujol mull), 11.8 kK; ν_{max} (in pyridine), 14.9 kK (log ϵ = 2.2); Calc. for (II) : C, 35.16; H, 2.19; Cl, 13.0; Cu, 23.26%.

$Cu_2(CH_3COO)_2(ASA-H)_2H_2O$, (III) : An ethanolic solution of copper(II) acetate dihydrate (1.0 g, 0.005 mole) was mixed with a solution of ASA-H₂ (1.6 g, 0.01 mole) in the same solvent at ~10° (pH of the mixture was ≈ 3). Immediately a light green crystalline precipitate was formed, washed with ice-cold ethanol and dried in a desiccator over fused CaCl₂. Found : C, 40.58; H, 3.48; Cu, 21.88%; μ_{eff} = 1.05 B.M. at 28.5°; ν_{max} (Nujol mull), 14.5 kK; ν_{max} (pyridine), 15.0 (log ϵ = 2.5); Calc. for (III) : C, 40.47; H, 3.03; Cu, 21.41%.

$Cu_2(ASA)_23H_2O$, (IV) : When an equimolar mixture of copper(II) acetate dihydrate, sodium carbonate and 3-aldehydosalicylic acid was refluxed (1 hr) in aqueous ethanol, this greenish blue crystalline complex was obtained, washed with water and ethanol. Found : C, 38.01; H, 2.88; Cu, 25.28%; μ_{eff} = 0.72 B.M. at 29° (per Cu atom); ν_{max} (Nujol mull), 14.3 kK; ν_{max} (pyridine) 14.2 kK (log ϵ = 1.8); Calc. for (IV) : C, 37.72; H, 2.75; Cu, 24.96%.

$Cu(ASAA-H)_2$, (V) : The pre-formed Schiff base, ASAA-H₂ (1.2 g; 0.005 mole) was dissolved in aqueous ethanol (50 ml; 50 : 50 v/v) containing calculated amount of sodium hydroxide. This solution, on treatment with the ethanolic solution (30 ml) of copper(II) acetate dihydrate (0.5 g; 0.0025 mole) under reflux, gave bright green crystalline silky precipitate, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried in vacuo. Found : C, 62.00; H, 3.29; N, 5.68; Cu, 12.08%; μ_{eff} = 1.80 B.M. at 27°; ν_{max} (Nujol mull), 16.6; 14.8 kK; Calc. for (V) : C, 61.81; H, 3.68; N, 5.15; Cu, 11.69%.

$Cu_2Cl_2(ASAA-H)_2$, (VI) : The reaction between the Schiff base and copper(II) chloride in 1 : 1 (or 1 : 2) molar proportions was carried out as described above. In both the cases the same green complex were isolated, washed with alcohol and dried in vacuo. The same complex was also isolated when stoichiometric amount of aniline was added to a refluxed solution of ASA-H₂ and CuCl₂·2H₂O (1 : 2 molar ratio) in absolute alcohol. Found : C, 49.22; H, 3.08; N, 4.47; Cl, 10.88; Cu, 19.00%; μ_{eff} = 1.12 B.M. at 28° (per Cu atom); ν_{max} (Nujol mull), 14.1 kK; ν_{max} (pyridine), 14.5 kK (log ϵ = 2.0); Calc. for (VI) : C, 49.56; H, 2.95; N, 4.13; Cl, 10.47; Cu, 18.74%.

$Cu_2(ASAMA)_2$, (VII) : To an aqueous solution (50 ml) of sodium carbonate (0.005 mole) containing ASA-H₂ (0.005 mole) and methylamine (0.005 mole) (70% aqueous solution was used), was added an aqueous solution of Cu(CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O (0.0025 mole). The mixture was heated on water-bath for 1 hr to yield blue crystalline complex, washed with water and aqueous ethanol. Found : C, 45.25; H, 3.06; N, 5.48; Cu, 26.88%; μ_{eff} = 0.71 B.M. at 28° (per Cu atom); ν_{max} (Nujol), 15.0 kK; ν_{max} (pyridine),

14.8 kK ($\log \epsilon = 2.0$); Calc. for (VII): C, 44.91; H, 2.91; N, 5.82; Cu, 26.40%.

[Cu(ASAENOL-H) $_2$ O] $_2$, (VIII): The sodium salt of the Schiff base ASAENOL-H $_2$ (0.5 g, 0.002 mole) was dissolved in 25 ml. of water and mixed with Cu(CH $_3$ COO) $_2$ ·2H $_2$ O (0.2 g; 0.001 mole) in 15 ml of water. The mixture was stirred at 60°–70° for 1 hr during which a bluish green silky precipitate was separated out. It was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried in a desiccator over fused CaCl $_2$. Found: C, 41.78; H, 3.50; N, 5.08; Cu, 21.87%; $\mu_{eff} = 0.60$ B.M. at 29° (per Cu atom); ν_{max} (Nujol), 15.5 kK; ν_{max} (pyridine), 15.4 kK ($\log \epsilon = 1.8$). Calc. for (VIII): C, 41.59; H, 3.81; N, 4.85; Cu, 22.01%.

Results and Discussion

Eight copper(II) complexes of 3-aldehydosalicylic acid and its Schiff bases with aniline, methylamine, and ethanolamine have been prepared, many of them are new. The complexes (I), (II), (III) and (VI) are not stable in contact with water, specially the complex (II) is extremely hygroscopic.

The magnetic moment data indicate that the present copper(II) complexes, except the complex Cu(ASAA-H) $_2$, (V), have subnormal magnetic properties. No appreciable change in μ_{eff} value has been observed in the complex (V) by changing temperature, while appreciable changes in μ_{eff} values have been observed for other complexes. Using g_{av} (2.2) 3 and a value 6×10^{-6} c.g.s. units for TIP, the $-2J$ values (which are energy separation between singlet and triplet states) of the complexes have been calculated according to the Bleaney and Bowers equation 5 . The values obtained for the complexes (III) ($-2J = 280$ cm $^{-1}$), (VI) ($-2J = 350$ cm $^{-1}$), and (VII) ($-2J = 710$ cm $^{-1}$) respectively. It is thus evident that the present copper(II) complexes exhibit a very strong antiferromagnetic spin-exchange interaction compared to the dihalogenobis (N-alkylsalicylaldiminato) dicopper(II) complexes. $^{6-10}$ The present magnetic data support a binuclear structure for the present complexes.

The electronic spectra (nujol mull) of the present copper(II) complexes, except the complex (V), have one d-d transition bands in the region 15,500–11,800 cm $^{-1}$. The complexes (I) to (III) in pyridine solution show appreciable change in d-d bands (to higher energy), although we have been unsuccessful to isolate any pyridine adducts of these complexes. However, it is noteworthy that the complexes (IV), (VII) and (VIII) in pyridine solutions show d-d bands to slightly lower-energy regions than that from the corresponding nujol mull spectrum. Since the shifts, however, are very small (100–200 cm $^{-1}$) and no splitting is observed in each spectrum, the complexes seem to keep binuclear structure in pyridine, in which no coordination of pyridine to the metal is supposed.

On the basis of electronic spectral data and magnetic moment value, a mono-nuclear structure may be proposed for the complex (V) 8,11 .

The i.r. spectra of some of the complexes have been measured. The coordinated $\nu_{C=N}$ bands for the Schiff base complexes (V) to (VIII) appeared in the range 1650–1640 cm $^{-1}$, while the bands for carboxylate groups in the complexes (I), (IV), (VII) and (VIII) are observed in the range 1550–1540 cm $^{-1}$. The skeletal vibration near 1500 cm $^{-1}$ is useful to distinguish the binuclear structure bridged by phenolic oxygen 6,12 . In the above mentioned complexes, however, this band could not be well recognised owing to the strong absorption of the carboxylate group. The complex (VII) does not show any band around 3400 cm $^{-1}$, while (VIII) exhibits bands in the range 3500–3000 cm $^{-1}$ indicating the presence of OH group. The coordinated $\nu_{C=O}$ (aldehyde group) bands appear in 1680–1650 cm $^{-1}$ range in the complex (I) to (IV), while $\nu_{C=O}$ (free carboxyl group) bands appeared in 1760–1740 cm $^{-1}$ range in the complexes (II) to (IV) and (VI). Besides these bands, the complex (III) shows ν_{as} (OCO) and ν_s (OCO) vibrations at 1615 cm $^{-1}$ and 1438 cm $^{-1}$ respectively, which demonstrates the presence of bridging acetate groups in these complexes. 13

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